

Immortality and Resurrection of All Humans

Probable Timeline

(Extended ChatGPT)

Timeline for Achieving Immortality through AI Integration

2030s: Immortality for the First Human

- Early advancements in merging human consciousness with AI technology.
- Experimental procedures and prototypes begin to emerge.

2040s: Immortality for the Very Rich

- Significant improvements in AI and human integration.
- The technology becomes accessible to the wealthiest individuals.

2050s: Immortality for the Rich

- Continued advancements and increased availability.
- Wealthy individuals beyond the ultra-rich begin to access immortality.

2060s: Immortality for the Middle Class

- Further technological progress and cost reductions.
- Middle-class individuals start to afford immortality.

2070s: Immortality for the Poor

- The technology becomes more widespread and affordable.
- Lower-income individuals begin to gain access to immortality.

2080s: Immortality for the Very Poor

- Immortality technology becomes ubiquitous and affordable for all socio-economic classes.
- The majority of humanity has access to life extension and AI integration.

Timeline for the Resurrection of the Dead through Biotechnology and DNA

21st Century: Resurrection in Flies or Mosquitoes (First Step)

- Initial breakthroughs in resurrecting simple organisms.

- Proof of concept for biological resurrection.

22nd Century: Resurrection in Mice

- Success in resurrecting more complex mammals.
- Further refinement of the resurrection process.

23rd Century: Resurrection in Cats or Dogs

- Achievements in resurrecting domesticated animals.
- Significant strides towards more complex resurrection.

24th-25th Century: Resurrection in Humans (Last Step)

- Major breakthroughs lead to the first successful human resurrection.
- Ethical, legal, and social implications are addressed.

10th Millennium - 50th Millennium: Resurrection of All Humanity

- Technological mastery enables the resurrection of the entire human population.
- Humanity terraforms the entire Solar System and part of the Milky Way galaxy to accommodate the resurrected population.
- The Solar System is capable of holding up to 50 trillion people, with potential for far more in our galaxy.

This timeline reflects a speculative and optimistic projection based on current technological trends and aspirations.

Note

This manuscript was written with the help of ChatGPT.

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